

Incorporation of Nanotechnology in Textile and its Economic and Environmental Aspects

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Abstract:

The investigation of materials having a length between 1 and 100 nanometers is known as nanotechnology (NT). When a material's dimensions are reduced to the nanoscale range, its characteristics significantly change. The textile industry is currently investigating the use of nanotechnology. With the goal to alter the physical, chemical, and biological properties of materials (atoms, molecules, and bulk matter) for the purpose to produce new materials, devices, structures, and systems that are better, we can define nanotechnology in the textile industry as the process of understanding, manipulating, and controlling matter at the above-mentioned length. It is employed to create textiles with the desired attributes, including high tensile strength, a distinct surface structure, a soft hand, durability, water repellency, fire retardancy, antimicrobial properties, etc. The development of nanotechnology in the textile industry has created a number of opportunities and challenges for the sector, all of which are thoroughly discussed in this article. The summary of contemporary applications of nanotechnology to textile fibres, textiles, and yarns is the primary goal of this work.

Keywords: Economic, Environmental, Fibres, Nanotechnology, Nanoparticles, Textile

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1. Introduction

Due to the widespread perception that nanotechnology holds enormous promise for a diverse variety of end uses, it is gaining more and more attention on a global scale. Due to their enormous economic potential, businesses have been interested in nanomaterials due to their novel and distinctive features [1-3].

The use of nano textile materials for numerous cutting-edge applications has recently been considered as having a significant promise. Nanoscience is the study of objects with dimensions smaller than a nanometer, or 10⁻⁹ (one millionth of a millimetre) [4]. Utilising nanoparticles and nanomaterials within cutting-edge products is known as nanotechnology. One of the most widespread uses of nanotechnology is in textiles. By utilising nanotechnology in textiles, innovative finishes and materials can be created that can be used for high-end applications like filtration down to the nanoscale, breathable sportswear, and protective fabrics for chemical and medical professionals.

The nanofibers exhibit a variety of advantageous properties, as previously mentioned, making them crucial in a wide range of applications. The most adaptable technology used today to create nano-scale materials is electrospinning. On the textile substrate, it is also used to engineer nanoscale materials. The nanomaterial created with this technology is highly porous and has a higher surface area, which makes it suitable for cutting-edge uses. By using a few unique suitable additives during electrospinning, a superior product for a particular purpose can be created.

Textile goods are already finding uses in a variety of technical and sophisticated application fields. Still, nanotechnology and nanoscience have already shown their usefulness in producing some textile materials as small

as a nanometer, showcasing highly porous fibres and high surface areas that demonstrate the appropriateness for cutting-edge applications. The majority of nanoscale textile products come in the type of nanomembranes or nanofibres. Due to their precisely designed structures and nanoscopic size, these materials have extraordinary capabilities that offer exceptional electrical, magnetic, optical, biological, thermal, and mechanical qualities.

The nanofibers can be created using a variety of methods, including centrifugal spinning, electrospinning, melt blowing, drawing, template synthesis, phase separation, and extrusion of biocomponents [5]. The successful application of nanofibers for tissue engineering, thermal resistance, biomedical products, filtration down to the nanoscale scale, protective equipment for military, chemical, and healthcare workers, and breathable sportswear is possible. These cutting-edge application textiles can be produced with success by incorporating nanofiber, nanoparticle, and nanotechnology additives into textiles.

2. Nanomaterials Needs

The standard textile methods have some restrictions that limit their ability to produce filaments beyond the microdenier range. A fabric made from these filaments won't have pores with a nanometer-sized diameter. This material should have more layers if we want the pore size to decrease as we increase both mass and thickness per unit area; as a result, it becomes more difficult to use in some advanced applications.

For instance, in the case of an artificial kidney, the membrane should permit the passage of waste material but should not permit the passage of valuable proteins or blood particles. Furthermore, the mass membrane should not permit any hazardous gas or microorganisms to get through. A nano-membrane is a material that is permeable and exhibits persistent impermeability to gases and water vapour as well as to any liquid or water.

Nanotechnology can be used to develop advanced effects on common textile products, such as durability, softness, and breathability. It can also be used to develop advanced properties, such as antimicrobial resistance, fire retardancy, water repellency, and various advanced applications in the medical field. This feature makes it easier to use them to create protective gear for medical professionals that provides both the necessary level of comfort and protection from any infectious fluids. Additionally, blood can be repelled by nanocoating in order to prevent accumulation of blood on medical personnel' protective garments as well as penetration of the clothes with blood. Since a regular textile material is unable to fulfil all of the aforementioned conditions, a nanomaterial is therefore required.

3. Application in properties of textile materials

Water repellency, soil resistance, wrinkle resistance, anti-bacterial, anti-static, and UV protection, flame retardancy, improved dye capacity, self-cleaning materials, and other qualities can be added to textiles using nanotechnology [6].

Figure 1: Nanotechnology in textile

Among them important applications are described below

3.1 Water Repellence

Nano-whiskers, which are hydrocarbons that are 1/1000 the size of a conventional cotton fibre and are added to the

fabric to generate a peach fuzz effect without reducing the strength of cotton, are created by Nano-Tex to increase the water-repellent ability of cloth. Water remains on top of the whiskers as well as above the fabric's surface because the gaps between the whiskers are less than a typical water drop but still bigger than water molecules. If pressure is applied, yet, liquid can still travel through the fabric. While still able to breathe, the performance is ongoing [7].

Figure 2: Water repellence in fabrics

3.2 UV Protective Finish

Protecting the wearer against the elements is one of the garment's most crucial tasks. However, it also serves to shield the wearer from the sun's damaging rays. The term "ultraviolet radiations" refers to light with a wavelength between 150 and 400 nm. A dye, pigment, delustrant, or ultraviolet absorber finish that absorbs ultraviolet radiation and prevents it from passing through a fabric to the skin improves a fabric's ability to block UV rays.

When opposed to organic UV-blocking compounds, metal oxides like ZnO are more stable. Nano ZnO will therefore significantly improve UV-blocking properties due to their increased surface area and high UV absorption. ZnO nanoparticles outperform nanosilver in terms of cost-effectiveness, whiteness, and UV-blocking ability for antibacterial finishing.

A person's exposure to UV rays is reduced and their skin is protected from potential damage by clothing made of fabric coated with UV absorbers to ensure that the garments reflect the sun's harmful ultraviolet radiation. The level of skin protection needed for various human skin types depends on the intensity & distribution of UV radiation in relation to geographic location, time of day, and season. SPF (Sun Protection Factor) is a measure of this protection; the greater the SPF value, the better the UV radiation protection [9-12].

Figure 3: Representation of UV protective finish

3.3 Self-cleaning Fabrics

Since 1990, stain-resistant jeans and khakis have been readily available, as have self-cleaning cotton fabrics known as nano-care and Nanotex. By altering the cylindrical structure of the cotton fibres that make up the fabric, nanocare textiles are produced. Cotton threads resemble tree trunks when viewed at the nanoscale. These tree trunks are covered in a fuzz of tiny whiskers made using nanotechnology, which surrounds the fibre with an air cushion. Water beading on the whiskers' points creates extra buoyancy by compressing the air in the spaces between the hairs as it contacts the cloth. Technically speaking, the cloth has been either extremely waterproof or extremely hydrophobic. There are fewer places of contact for dirt because of the whiskers. When water is put to filthy fabric, the dirt is transported away with the water as it beads up and rolls off the surface of the fabric because the dirt sticks to the water far better than it sticks to the textile surface. Thus, the lotus plant's leaves serve as the foundation for the idea of soil-cleaning [13].

Figure 4: View of self-cleaning fabrics

3.4 Anti-static Finishes

Because synthetic fibres like nylon and polyester absorb little water, static charge typically accumulates in these materials. As a result, no static charge can build up since cellulosic fibres have more water in them that carries away static charges. Due to the poor anti-static qualities of synthetic fibres, research was done on how to improve the anti-static properties of textiles using nanotechnology. It was shown that synthetic fibres might acquire anti-static qualities by incorporating nano-sized titanium dioxide, zinc oxide whiskers, antimony-doped tin oxide (ATO), and silane nano sol. TiO_2 , ZnO , and ATO are electrically conductive materials that have anti-static properties. This type of material effectively dissipates the static charge that has built up on the fabric. On the other hand, silane nano sol enhances anti-static qualities because the silane gel particles on the fibre absorb moisture from the air through amino and hydroxyl groups as well as bound water [14, 15].

Figure 5: Effect of anti- static finishes

3.5 Nano Technology for Wrinkle Free Treatment

In an effort to give an alternative to abrasive conventional methods, Nano-Text has introduced a novel wrinkle-free

treatment based on nanotechnology that promises to improve performance while maintaining the strength and integrity of the fabric. A fabric's rip and tensile strength are decreased by chemicals and processing techniques. This means that some fabrics and clothing items, including lightweight fabrics or slim-fitting clothing, are traditionally not candidates for wrinkle-free technology, despite the fact that they are popular and handy for consumers who are short on time. In other cases, materials must be over-engineered or strengthened in order to withstand the fibre deterioration brought on by conventional wrinkle-free techniques. Either way, present technologies are ineffective for all materials or the brand/retailer must spend more money to account for the damaging effects of wrinkle-free chemistry.

Figure 6: Before and after wrinkle free treatment view

The new Fortify DP technology from Nano-Tex uses a molecular structure at the nanoscale to permeate the fibre more deeply and enhance wrinkle-free performance. It also makes use of a longer and more flexible cross-linking chain, which lowers the tensional load on the fibre and, consequently, the major strength loss connected to conventional wrinkle-free chemistry [16-18].

3.6 Anti-bacterial Finishes

Nano-sized zinc oxide, titanium dioxide, and silver are employed to provide anti-bacterial characteristics. Metallic ions and metallic compounds have certain sterilizing properties. According to this theory, a portion of the oxygen in the air or water is catalyzed by the metallic ion to become active oxygen, which dissolves the organic material to have a sterilizing effect. The number of particles per unit area is increased when nanoscale particles are used, maximizing the antibacterial effects [19-21].

Figure 7: Effect of moisture regain on the refractive index of fibers

3.7 Market needs of nanomaterials

Because of their enormous economic potential, nanomaterials' distinctive features have drawn not just scientists and researchers, but also corporations. The market for products inspired by nanotechnology is being driven by society's rising acceptance of the technology. This emphasises the need to comprehend the potential effects these items may have on the environment, the eco-system, animals, and people. The global market for nanomaterials was valued at 8.5 billion US dollars in 2019; from 2020 to 2027, it is expected to increase at a rate of 13.1% annually. The rapid acceptance and adoption of nanostructures in the aerospace applications, medical and health sectors, food and packaging industry, agriculture and farming, sports, cosmetics, constructions, paints and coatings, electronics, environmental remediation, power and energy sectors, etc. is credited with this increase in nanotechnology's market share. The distinctive physical, chemical, and biological features of metal nanoparticles are the driving force behind this expanding industry for nanomaterials. Many different consumer items use copper, silver, platinum, gold, aluminium, palladium, zinc, tellurium, titanium metals, as well as their oxide-based nanoparticles and carbon-based nanostructures.

Table 1: Estimated growth rate of whole world and USA

Revenues in \$ billions	Annual growth rate 2000–2010	Annual growth rate 2010–2013	Estimated growth for year 2020	Estimated growth for year 2030
World	25%	48%	3000	30,000
USA	24%	38%	750	7500

Source: data from Roco et al. and from Lux Research

The USA and China are at the top of the list of nations investing in nanotechnology, which is a global phenomenon. The process of incorporating produced nanomaterials into the final market product is being rendered by this influx of cash. The market for nanotechnology is predicted to expand with a 17% CAG rate in the seven years between 2018 and 2025 with this interest and funding. The upbeat market trend is a result of the thoughtful partnerships between science, business, and society [22, 23].

4. The Environmental Impact of Nanotechnology

Global environmental concerns include raising the standard of the air, soil, and water. Industry is currently concentrating on locating pollutants (from chemical spills, fertiliser runoff, and pesticide runoff), enhancing industrial and mining sites, treating toxins, and halting further pollution. Nanomaterials could be a viable answer to these issues. Nanomaterials can be utilised to help clean the environment and even offer effective energy solutions, like solar cells made of nanomaterials. Additionally, nanoparticles contribute to the enhancement of numerous consumer goods' functionality and quality. As a result, produced nanoparticles are being exposed to more people every day. However, nanotechnology has both beneficial and harmful effects on the environment [24-27].

4.1 Positive Impacts

Water quality can be enhanced with the aid of nanotechnology. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs), zeolites, nanoparticles of zero valent iron (ZVI), silver nanoparticles, and other nanomaterials are a few examples of nanomaterials that can be employed for water remediation. Other nanomaterials, such as tungsten oxide, titanium dioxide, and zinc oxide, act as photocatalysts. These photocatalysts have the ability to oxidise organic contaminants into inert substances. Due to its strong photostability, high photoconductivity, availability, affordability, and non-toxicity, TiO₂ is the material of choice. Nanoscale silver has an antibacterial effect. Additionally, a lot of polymeric nanoparticles are employed to treat wastewater.

Nanofiltration is another cutting-edge technology that can be used to clean water in homes, businesses, and other industrial settings. An energy-efficient membrane that filters five times as much water as traditional ones is made of molybdenum disulphide (MoS₂). A paper towel made of nanofabric that is woven from small wires of potassium manganese oxide that can absorb oil 20 times its weight has been created to clean up oil spills in water bodies. Nanotechnology thus offers a way to treat the polluted water and stop further pollution.

Nanotechnology can be used to purify airborne hazardous gases. But first, we need to use precise sensors to locate the pollutants at the molecular level. Heavy metal ions and radioactive elements can both be detected by a sensor known as a nanocontact sensor. These sensors are portable, affordable, and simple to use on-site. Currently, NO₂ and NH₃ gas detection is done using single-walled nanotubes (SWNTs). In addition, compared to conventional sensors, which operate between 200 and 600 °C, SWNTs sensors may achieve high sensing activity at room temperature. For the detection of pesticides, heavy metals, and VOCs, cantilever sensors have been created. Toxic gases including NO_x, SO₂, and CO₂ can be adsorbed using a mixture of CNTs and gold particles. Another porous nanomaterial manganese oxide has better adsorption of toxic gases due to its large surface area.

Therefore, we may contribute to the sustainability of both human health and the environment by identifying contaminants using particular sensors. As a result, nanotechnology offers us a fresh method for reducing waste generation, greenhouse gas emissions, and the release of harmful chemicals into waterways.

4.2 Negative Impacts

Nanomaterials may potentially be detrimental. The relative environmental danger of the produced nanomaterials is now poorly understood. There are no precise standards to measure the impacts, and only a few studies have been done to determine the direct and indirect exposure to nanomaterials.

The National Science Foundation and the US Environmental Protection Agency recently organised a workshop to determine the crucial risk concerns relating to nanoparticles. Determine exposure and toxicity of produced nanoparticles, ability to extrapolate toxicity of made nanoparticles using current particle and fibre toxicology database, and recyclability and overall sustainability of the created nanomaterials were the specific goals of the workshop.

4.3 Green Technology

Utilising green technology or green production is a corrective measure. This technique was created with the environment in mind and is employed to preserve natural resources. With the use of fewer raw materials, less energy, and less waste, this method promises to produce nanomaterials. Every manufacturing process is known to produce a significant quantity of trash. Green production, which employs environmentally friendly chemicals and energy-saving techniques, reduces this to a minimum. Green technology includes microemulsions, which are utilised in place of VOCs in the cleaning sector.

As a result, scientists are keeping an eye on the different nanoparticles that are created and employed, as well as the effects that follow. This is done to strike a balance between the advantages of the technology and any potential negative effects [28].

5. Nanotechnology's Future Potential in the Textile Industry

As an enabling technology, nanotechnology improves the effectiveness and efficiency of the current applications. Nanomaterials have a huge future potential because they have the ability to be employed for a variety of cutting-edge applications across many industries. The companies are now concentrating on producing nano-textile goods that have conventional qualities and adhere to global standards for safety, health, and the environment. Given the increased consumer interest in nano-textiles and the stringent environmental regulations, it is crucial for textile producers to maintain high ethical standards in these goods. Technology has historically been incorporated into textiles, as is evident.

For example, efforts have been made to enhance clothes with sensing capabilities further. Companies are also

working on developing textile-based nano-sensors, which opens up a wide range of opportunities for the nano-textile, including the development of clothing that is easily adaptable to changing weather conditions, monitoring wearers' vital signs, and creating specialised healthcare systems.

One of the issues with the development of nano-textiles is the high expenses of the technology. Thermos- or temperature-regulated clothing is a common appearance in the garment market, but customers avoid it because of the high cost. Despite some drawbacks, nanotechnology has a wide range of benefits, including the capacity to provide textile items improved corrosion-resistance capabilities while also making them more durable, lighter, and stronger. The future of nanotechnology in the textile industry is looking bright, according to research that focuses on enhancing its prospects or developing exceptional textile functions [29-32].

6. Conclusion

Thanks to the development of technology for the manufacture of nanomaterials, a customised product can now be produced more quickly and with the required features. It is now simpler to use textile nanoparticles for cutting-edge applications. The use of nanotechnology in cutting-edge textile applications is already well known in the textile industry. The textile sector has a bright future for nanotechnology and will use it extensively.

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